

Demo: Ambient Backscatter Communication with Convolutional Code based on LTE Pilots

Jingyi Liao*, Kalle Ruttik*, Riku Jäntti*, and Dinh-Thuy Phan-Huy†

*Department of Communications and Networking, Aalto University, 02150 Espoo, Finland

Email: {jingyi.liao, kalle.ruttik, riku.jantti}@aalto.fi

†Networks, Orange Innovation, Chatillon, France

Email: dinhthuy.phanhuy@orange.com

Abstract—Ambient Backscatter Communication (AmBC) is a low power communication technique that reflects or absorbs the ambient signal, i.e., Long Term Evolution (LTE) downlink Cell-specific Reference Signal (CRS). Information of Backscatter Devices (BDs) is conveyed on ambient signal without requiring additional power, which is promising for energy-autonomous devices. In practical scenarios, AmBC works under a severe SNR conditions with low Bit Error Rate (BER). This paper introduces the feasibility of convolutional channel coded AmBC to improve BER performance with LTE CRS assisted. Compared with uncoded modulation, the convolutional channel coding yields approximately 5 dB of gain at a BER of 10^{-2} . AmBC demonstrates reliability, achieving a BER of 10^{-3} at an SNR of 5 dB.

Keywords—Ambient Backscatter Communications, LTE Cell Specific Reference Signals, Channel Estimation, Convolutional coding

I. INTRODUCTION

The 6G flagship Hexa-X II [1] is exploring a zero-energy communication solution for Ambient Internet of Things (AIoT). The technique of Ambient Backscatter Communication (AmBC) is a promising technology demanding Zero Energy Devices (ZEDs), utilizing the energy present in the environment. In the AmBC approach, the Backscatter Device (BD) does not generate RF signals but carries its information on ambient RF signals, such as LTE downlink signals, by toggling between two reflection and absorption states. The modulation of the propagation channel technique decreases transmitter power by several orders of magnitude compared with those active transmitters.

However, the price of borrowing ambient RF power is that BD signals from the scattered path are extremely weak compared to ambient signals from the direct path, which is interfered with the direct path interference (DPI). To resist DPI, the study [2] discusses Long Term Evolution (LTE) Cell-specific Reference Signal (CRS) assisted Frequency Shift Keying (FSK) modulation. The challenge of that AmBC method is that the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) in practice is too low to achieve a reasonable Bit Error Rate (BER). The aim of this study is to improve that AmBC approach's BER under a low SNR scenario, with convolutional coding gains.

In this demonstration, we utilize a User Equipment (UE)-assisted AmBC and reuse the convolutional coding tool already existing in 3GPP LTE specifications [3] to prove the feasibility of proposed channel code method (Fig. 2). By leveraging LTE

CRS, the UE estimates the propagation channel and identifies channel changing caused by BD, facilitating information transmission from BD to UE. Subsequently, AmBC receiver is integrated in UE, comprising an independent demodulator and a reused LTE decoder.

II. METHODS

The signal flow chart, including modulation and coding, is illustrated in Fig. 1. Firstly, a Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) is added at the tail of IoT information. Subsequently, it undergoes convolutional coding. Finally a synchronization header is appended at the beginning of frame packet. Compared with uncoded FSK modulation proposed in [2], the modulation and synchronization header remain unchanged, but channel coding and CRC are introduced as additional components.

1) *FSK modulation*: The BD alternates between two load impedances, reflecting or absorbing incident RF signals. This switching is known as on-off key (OOK) modulation. By varying the switching speed of the BD, the symbols are coded into binary FSK, approximated as square waves. In this paper, the symbol duration of FSK is 40 ms, and the FSK frequency keys are 250 Hz and 625 Hz, respectively.

2) *Synchronization*: The BD transmits data packets blindly, without any knowledge of LTE downlink symbol. Consequently, the packets arrive to UE randomly. Therefore, the receiver requires a header to synchronize the frame for FSK symbol demodulation. A synchronization header consisting of three 7-bit Barker codes is attached at the beginning of convolutional coded symbols.

3) *Channel coding*: The data package is encoded with a 1/3 rate convolutional code, which is reused from LTE control channel's 1/3 rate convolutional coding [3]. On the UE side, the soft-decision Viterbi decoder is embedded in advance for LTE control channel. The AmBC receiver leverages this existing decoder.

4) *Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC)*: A 16-bit CRC-CCITT [3] is appended to the tail of IoT information bits. The AmBC receiver utilizes the same 16-bit CRC-CCITT specification as in LTE [3]. The CRC is attached for the detection and correction of received information bits.

The purpose of channel coding and CRC is to make AmBC robust even in the low SNR scenario in practice environments. We reuse the 1/3 rate convolutional code and 16-bit CRC-CCITT to decrease the implementation costs of the AmBC

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the proposed AmBC transmitter and receiver.

Fig. 2. An illustration of the measurement setup.

receiver. Further discussion about channel coding method, CRC length, and other parameters are elaborated upon [4].

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

A wireless AmBC measurement has been validated in a real commercial LTE environment [4]. However, in this demonstration we simply use cables without a frequency license over-the-air as shown in Fig. 2. This wireless propagation process is simulated using cables, attenuators and a circulator. The direct path from BS to UE with attached attenuator 1 represents the wireless direct path. The scattered path from BS to UE via BD with attached attenuator 0 mimics the BD-modulated scattered path over-the-air. The scattered path is modulated by BD, carrying IoT information to the ambient signal. Two Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) function as BS and UE separately.

One USRP, labeled as Tx, sends LTE downlink CRS signal, while the other USRP, labeled as Rx, continuously synchronizes with CRS and estimates the propagation channel, replicating the real LTE BS to UE downlink synchronization and channel estimation process. Subsequently, the channel estimates from Rx USRP are transmitted to the computer. Then, the MATLAB receiver independently executes AmBC receiver algorithm after LTE receiver.

The measurement campaign collected 21,800 valid packets in total. The x-axis SNR is defined as the scattered signal power to the noise power ratio in channel estimates. The SNR of each packet is recorded, and then those packets are classified into 0.25 SNR intervals, as shown in Fig. 4. The error bits with in each 0.25 dB interval are counted in one BER point, as depicted in Fig 3. It shows the AmBC BER performance of uncoded FSK modulation and convolutional channel coding. Additionally, the theoretical FSK noncoherent detector BER curve and Monte Carlo 1/3 rate convolutional code BER curve are provided as references.

Fig. 3. Measured SNR and BER.

Fig. 4. Number of received valid packet under different SNR interval.

In Fig. 4, we observe that the SNR typically ranges from -5 dB to 5 dB in most cases. However, in this scenario, the performance of uncoded FSK noncoherent detector is worse than 10^{-1} BER, which is not practical. To enhance the reliability of this AmBC, the channel coding is introduced, achieving 10^{-3} BER at 5 dB SNR. The AmBC with channel coding is more useful and reasonable performance in most practical situations. In Fig. 3, the coding gain is about 5 dB under 10^{-2} BER.

This measurement results prove the feasibility of channel coding AmBC under ordinary SNR situations. The BER of this AmBC system achieves 10^{-3} BER at 5 dB SNR in practice, with the help of convolutional code and CRC. The 1/3 rate convolutional coding and 16-bit CRC-CCITT, reused from LTE specifications, bring about a 5 dB gain under 10^{-2} BER situation.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is in part supported by the European Project Hexa-X II under (grant 101095759) and Business Finland Project eMTC (Dnro 8028/31/2022).

REFERENCES

- [1] "Hexa-X II deliverable D5.2 characteristics and classification of 6G device classes," 2023. [Online]. Available: https://hexa-x-ii.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Hexa-X-II_D5.2_final.pdf
- [2] J. Liao, X. Wang, K. Ruttik, R. Jantti, and D.-T. Phan-Huy, "In-band ambient fsk backscatter communications leveraging lte cell-specific reference signals," *IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification*, vol. 7, pp. 267–277, 2023.
- [3] 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), "Multiplexing and channel coding," Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA), Technical Specification TS 36.212, Sep. 2023, version 18.0.0.
- [4] J. Liao, K. Ruttik, R. Jantti, and P.-H. Dinh-Thuy, "Coded backscattering communication with LTE pilots as ambient signal," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.12657*, 2024.